

PHILOLOGY: LEXICOLOGY

THE USE OF OBSOLETE WORDS IN TOLEPBERGEN QAYIPBERGENOV'S
SHORT STORY "COLD DROP"

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ANNOTATION:

The current state: One of the issues studied in the knowledge of the Karakalpak language is analyzed through the prism of linguistic criticism, such as archaism, ishtarism, and dialectalism. In the article, the linguistic criticism elucidates the usage of obsolete words in our language in a vivid literary style, emphasizing the linguistic aspect.

Subject: Objects are comprised of obsolete words and dialectal words in the language of Karakalpak, and they are analyzed.

Purpose: Learning the usage of obsolete words in our language, their requirements, analysis, and usage in literary works. Supplement. Learning the significant usage of obsolete words in the language of literary works.

Methodology: Comparative and descriptive analysis.

Results: Learning obsolete words and dialectal words, creating their contemporary and comparative forms, and usage.

Conclusions: The functional differentiation of dialectal and obsolete words in our language has been shaped, and through the introduction of new terms, the vocabulary of our language is enriched.

Key words: Obsolete words, archaism, ishtarism, semantics, lexicology.

In the narratives of historical upheavals of the people, new meanings and concepts are expressed through new terms - neologisms, while on the contrary, basic words - terms, gradually gain usage, and eventually emerge as distinct from common usage. Archaic terms form a group of obsolete words and enter the passive vocabulary. With the passage of time, synonyms of archaisms may emerge in the vocabulary structure, and they become active, shaping the usage of archaisms. Archaic terms given to other words in the lexicon are called lexical archaisms, while the differentiated meanings of many meaningful words are referred to as semantic archaisms.

Words that have emerged from usage and deviated from common usage in the structure of the language's vocabulary - obsolete words are studied and classified in Russian linguistics, and several works have been written on this subject. In the works of A. Mahmudov, E. Abdilbaev, and E. Qilichev, obsolete words have been extensively analyzed. In the field of Kazakh linguistics, A. Bolganbayev's contribution to the lexicon of the Kazakh language has been taken as an example, and it has been divided into thematic groups based on thematic topics.

Moreover, in the comprehensive research of Professor E. Berdimuratov, lessons were devoted to the lexicon of the Karakalpak language. In the author's work "Lexicology of Contemporary Karakalpak," obsolete words are divided into historical words and archaisms, highlighting their distinct characteristics. Obsolete words in the Karakalpak language are studied in comparison with contemporary words (neologisms), teaching them to students, emphasizing the meanings of these words and the usage of enriched expressions in the language. It is of great importance to teach students the meaning and usage of these words in the language of literary works.

Obsolete words are also shown to be used in the literary style of contemporary literature. Writers and poets use obsolete words in their literary works to convey the unique flavor of the region, reflecting the special language diversity of the region.

For example, when we analyze the "Cold Drop" story by the writer Tolepbergen Qayipbergenov, we can observe the effective use of obsolete words in terms of lexicosemantic aspects. Historical and archaic words used in this work are still relevant today. However, their meanings are often enriched by new words (neologisms). In this context, let me explain the meanings of the words used in the work more broadly:

1. Numerous individuals near this deteriorated, aged, and shabby residence experience

considerable happy.

2. Late at night, the clandestine conversations of couples, the laughter of gathered youth, and the voices of men and women can be heard, carrying a sense of celebration in the air.

3. We stopped next to a mature woman in her 80s, with fair and delicate skin, dressed in a golden attire, resembling a woman in her mid-40s or 50s who was next to her stood a young girl with a jingling braid.

4. "The owner of the house, come, my beloved and kind person is waiting over there," he said.

5. I wandered a little and then I showed Kalinin street with my chin.

6. Next to us are desert plants: haloxylon, kosuk, halostachys mixed pseudalhagi.

7. If the floor had cracked now, I would have come in.

8. On these days, in a dream, Ziyada walked around inside our new room, hesitated if it darkened me, and fell many times at night from the bed.

9. I began to hate this dishonest person.

10. When it comes to cleaning, the essential tools for my work are: a dustpan, a broom, a mop, a bucket, a dust cloth, and a brush.

11. "Oh, what a catastrophe!" I exclaimed, kicking the box with the heel.

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| 1. | Meñirew: Craftiness. The ability to think and act wisely, not being deceived easily. |
| 2. | Jupit: Clear. Horses, well-fed and well-groomed. |
| 3. | Gezhi: Clear. A type of headgear made from the felt of a young sheep. |
| 4. | Qaywana: Clear. A middle-aged person with intelligence, wisdom, and the ability to give advice on various matters. |
| 5. | Otağasy: Clear. A venerable elder with a large family. |
| 6. | Gidirw: Verb. To wait eagerly, to be patient, to endure. |
| 7. | Qösiq: Clear. A type of herb that grows in the sand, used as a seasoning. |
| 8. | Eden: Clear. The internal courtyard and living space of a traditional Kazakh yurt, |

adapted for various activities.

9. **Gölegeyw**: Verb. To gently touch or caress one thing against another, creating a pleasant sound.
10. **Naysap**: Clear. Dirty, messy, chaotic, disorganized.
11. **Sozan**: Clear. The type of a large headgear worn by noble women.
12. **Atawyz**: Clear. A traditional game.
13. **Qobdiy**: Clear. A tool used by skilled workers to cut leather.

Language is an ever-evolving and dynamic phenomenon. It constantly adapts and develops in various spheres of life. It is enriched and expands in every cultural environment. The unique words in the language are widely used, while some gradually fade away from common usage. Words that have remained in use are considered enriched, and those that have fallen out of common use are classified as archaic. The remaining words in our language that are not in common use are categorized as obsolete words. Obsolete words in the language are carefully studied in terms of their historical and literary significance.

Obsolete words reflect the lexical richness of the language, and their usage by writers in their works adds to the language's lexical diversity. The writer Toleubergen Qayipbergenov, through his skillful use of obsolete words that are now rarely used, contributes to the uniqueness of the Karakalpak language. Learning these obsolete words and understanding their meanings contribute to the refinement of our language. This work, though modest, aims to contribute to the future enrichment of the Karakalpak language by providing explanations of obsolete words based on the writer's works.

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